

Eighteen traditional varieties had a damage rating of 1 in preliminary screening. They were retested to confirm resistance.

Treatments (varieties) were arranged in a randomized complete block design replicated five times. The resistant and susceptible checks were sown randomly among test entries. Water level was slightly increased at 7 DAS and maintained at the proper level. When susceptible check TN1 showed a rating of 7 at 20 DAS, 20 seedlings/replication were removed at random. Thrips were counted in each seedling under a binocular microscope and expressed as a mean population of thrips/seedling.

All of the selected traditional varieties had a low thrip population at 20 DAS, and all, except Vali, had a damage rating of 1, indicating a high level of resistance to thrips (see table). ■

Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) biotype in Karimnagar District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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The local gall midge (GM) Asian population at Agricultural Research Station, Warangal, AP, has biotype1 pattern and a resistant reaction to all three groups of differential donors (Eswarakora, Siam 29, and Veleuthacheera/Banglei derivatives). Since 1988, however, widespread GM incidence has been reported in resistant varieties Surekha and Phalguna in the adjacent district of Karimnagar. An experiment to examine GM biotype under natural field infestation was conducted during 1992 and 1993 wet seasons (WS) at RARS.

Eleven differential donors, constituting three different resistance groups, were obtained from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. Entries were transplanted in single rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing during the second week of Aug

Table 1. Reaction of differentials to GM population at RARS, Jagtial, AP, India. 1992 and 1993 WS.

Group	Entry	Differential donor	Incidence at 50 d after transplanting			
			Silvershoots on a tiller basis (%)		Damaged plants on a hill basis (%)	
			1992	1993	1992	1993
I	1	W1263	0	0	0	0
	2	ARC6605	0	0	0	0
II	3	Phalguna	30	26	100	95
	4	ARC5984	20	18	100	100
	5	Surekha	12	20	100	100
III	6	CR-MR-1523	3	0	40	0
	7	Velluthacheera	0	0	0	0
	8	Aganni	0	0	0	0
	9	Ptb10	0	0	0	0
IV	10	T1477	0	0	0	0
	11	TN1 (susceptible check)	38	30	100	100

Table 2. Reaction of different rice varieties and cultures to GM population in multilocation trials. RARS, Jagtial, Karimnagar, AP, India, 1992 WS.

Variety/culture	Parentage	Source of resistance	Reaction
Kakatiya	IR8/W1263	Eswarakora	Resistant
Pothana	IR579/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
Kavya (WGL 48684)	WGL 27120/WGL 17672 /Mahsuri/Surekha	Eswarakora and Siam 29	Resistant
Divya (WGL 44645)	WGL 23022/Surekha	Eswarakora	Resistant
Erramallelu (WGL 20471)	BC5-W/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
Dhanyalaxmi (BPT1235)	BC5-W/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
WGL 18011-15	CR44/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
Surekha	IR8/Siam 29	Siam 29	Susceptible
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	Siam 29	Susceptible
WGL 3962	Phalguna/IR36	Siam 29	Susceptible
WGL 3943	Phalguna/IR50	Siam 29	Susceptible

1992 and third week of Aug 1993 to favor high GM infestation. TN1 was used as the susceptible check. GM incidence was recorded for each entry by counting damaged hills, total tillers, and silvershoots at 50 d after transplanting.

GM incidence was heavy during 1992 WS. The group II differentials, Phalguna, ARC5984, and Surekha, and TN1 showed 100% damaged plants on a hill basis and 30, 20, 12, and 38% silvershoots, respectively, on a tiller basis. The group I differentials, W1263 and ARC6605, and group III differentials, CR-MR-1523, Velluthacheera, Aganni, and Ptb10, were free from GM

attack, except for CR-MR-1523, which had 40% damaged plants and 3% silvershoots.

A similar trend was noticed during 1993 WS. In group II differentials, Phalguna had 95% damaged plants with 2.6% silvershoots and ARC5984 and Surekha had 100% damaged plants with 18 and 20% silvershoots, respectively, compared with 100% damaged plants and 30% silvershoots in TN1. The other group I and II differentials were completely free from GM attack (Table 1).

In addition, previously GM-resistant varieties Phalguna and Surekha, derivatives of Siam 29, started showing

susceptibility in 1988 at RARS, Jagtial, and surrounding villages.

High GM incidence was observed in multilocation varietal trials during 1992 WS in Siam 29 derivatives Phalguna, Surekha, WGL 3962, and WGL 3943. Eswarakora derivatives were resistant (Table 2).

Phalguna, Surekha, and ARC5984, differentials derived from Siam 29 and belonging to group II, were susceptible to the local GM population in Karimnagar District in 1992-93, indicating a change in the pattern of reaction from biotype 1 to one similar to that of biotype 3. ■

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* in coastal Karnataka, India

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Gall midge (GM) is increasing in incidence in the coastal region of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka State. We screened 50 promising cultures for resistance during 1992-93 wet seasons (WS).

Cultures were transplanted in 4-m rows spaced at 20 cm. We recorded the number of tillers and percentage showing silvershoots 50 d after transplanting for 10 randomly selected hills per row. Ten entries were resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to GM infestation in the field, Karnataka, India, 1992-93 WS.

Av silvershoots (%)	Lines
0-5	IET9691, IET11475, IET12179, IET12351, IET12797, IET12811, IR36, Abhaya, Suraksha, Shakthi
5-10	IET9683, IET10851, IET10318, IET11151, IET11375, IET11467, IET12186, IET12187, IET12188, IET12191, IET12419, H4, Sasyasree, Kasturi, Pusa Basmati 1, Jaldi 2, Jaldi 3
10-20	IET9553, IET10265, IET10720, IET11466, IET12183, IET12190, Jaldi 1, Jaldi 4, PNR162, PNR166, PNR519, PNR546, PNR381, IR22 (R), Ratna, Vibhava, Vikas, Mangala, Rasi
20 or more	Sonasali, Avinash, IR20, Jaya (check)

Stress tolerance

Response of rice plants from different regions to ultraviolet-B radiation

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Increased ultraviolet-B (UV-B) radiation (280-320 nm), as a result of stratospheric ozone depletion, has damaging effects on several plant physiological processes including photosynthesis, carbohydrate status, ion uptake, and ultimately, dry matter production. Species and varietal differences, in terms of sensitivity to enhanced UV-B, have been reported. Varietal differences have been noted in rice. It is possible that land races and cultivars originating from high UV-B areas have greater tolerance.

We tested the hypothesis that rice cultivars originating from regions with higher ambient UV-B radiation are more tolerant of UV-B radiation by evaluating their growth response to elevated UV-B radiation.

We screened 188 rice cultivars from various varietal groups and ecosystems, supplied by the International Rice

Number of rice cultivars in a group showing a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in plant height, tiller number, leaf area, and dry weight when exposed to 3 wk of enhanced UV-B radiation.

Group	Number of cultivars	Plant height	Tiller number	Leaf area	Dry weight
Indica	117	87 (74) ^a	26 (22)	39 (33)	40 (34)
Japonica ^b	55	42 (76)	8 (15)	15 (27)	13 (24)
Javanica ^b	7	5 (71)	5 (71)	3 (43)	3 (43)
Hybrid	9	9 (100)	2 (25)	5 (73)	5 (73)
Total	188	143 (76)	41 (22)	62 (28)	61 (32)

^aValues in parentheses represent the percentage of cultivars affected. ^bJaponica and javanica groups do not differ by isozyme analysis.

Germplasm Center at IRRI, for their growth response to UV-B treatment from 1991 to 1992. Cultivars were screened in batches of 22. Seeds were pregerminated at 30 °C for 24 h and then sown in 1-liter plastic pots containing 1.7 kg of Maahas clay soil fertilized with 0.4 g N, 0.04 g P, and 0.25 g K/kg soil.

Plants were grown in the greenhouse for 10 d and then subjected to UV-B treatment for 3 wk in a temperature- and humidity-controlled glasshouse (day/night temperature = 27/21 °C; relative humidity = 70%). UV-emitting fluorescent lamps supplied the UV-B radiation. Plants were irradiated for 6 h/d

(0900-1500 h). The average biologically effective UV-B radiation ($UV-B_{BE}$) was 13.0 kJ/m² per d. Six plants (2 pots) from each of the four replications were sampled after 3 wk of UV-B treatment. Plant height, tiller number, leaf area, leaf dry weight, and culm dry weight were determined. Plant dry weight was the sum of leaf and culm dry weight. The differences between the treated plant and corresponding control were analyzed using LSD test. The ambient UV-B radiation of origin was calculated based on latitude, longitude, and growing season according to the Björn and Murphy model.